

The Inseparable Union of Religion and Economy: A Critical Analysis

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Abstract:

The growth of economy is seen as a fundamental measurement that can be used to assess a country's productive capacity in terms of goods and services. It is normally predicted using the percent rate of increase in gross domestic product (GDP) per capita and is correlated with numerous factors in the society which includes quality of life. Religion as a prominent dimension of culture can be a considerable factor in one's quality of life. However, it is often overlooked as a potential determinant of economic growth but it has been underscored that it helps in boosting the economic growth of the society. In this work therefore, a cursory effort will be made to divulge some of those roles religion plays in her contribution to a better economy and to examine how religious activities or policies of some religious traditions affect or boost the economy of a given section of the society. Phenomenological approach was adopted in this study and the theory of Religious Economy was used. The paper recommends based on findings that religion should not be seen in isolation as it helps to determine the growth of the economy of every given society.

Keywords: inseparable, union, religion, economy, critical analysis.

Introduction

Religions are ever-present across human societies. According to Campante and Yanagizawa-Drott (2015), it is natural to speculate that they may affect important economic outcomes, such as economic growth as many have done dating at the very least to Weber's celebrated work. While this possibility is certainly appealing, assessing its prevalence and importance is a rather complicated task, both conceptually and empirically, because religions are multifaceted social phenomena whose different aspects could most likely have different effects.

Religious practice is an efficient and effective catalyst of socio-economic growth. In the United States, religious organizations produce substantial economic revenue and substantial social capital through its civic and social networks and foster human capital growth in its citizens. According to a 2016 estimate, faith-based organisations in the U.S. had greater revenue than that of Apple and Microsoft combined. It can be said that any decline in religious practice of any society is laddened with significant negative repercussions in that society.

From the perspective of an individual consumer, religious expression is economic goods that must compete with all other goods for a share of the resource budget. It is not goods in the material sense, but rather an intangible one for which people express a preference by their willingness to spend time and money on its acquisition. Nor is it goods that can be purchased in a consumption-ready form. It belongs to the category of economic goods that must be self-produced by each individual. The consumer may buy goods and services that contribute to this end, but must spend his or her own time to use them in a way that creates a religious experience.

Understanding the Key Words

Religion according to Morreall and Tamara (2013) is a cultural system of designated behaviours and practices, morals, worldviews, texts, sanctified places, prophecies, ethics, or organisations, that relates humanity to supernatural, transcendental, or spiritual elements. However, there is no scholarly consensus over what precisely constitutes a religion.

James and Mandaville (2010) posit that different religions may contain various elements ranging from the divine, sacred things, faith, a supernatural being or 'some sort of ultimacy and transcendence that will provide norms and power for the rest of life'. Religious practices may include rituals, sermons, commemoration or veneration (of deities), sacrifices, festivals, feasts, trances, initiations, funerary services, matrimonial services, meditation, prayer, music, art, dance, public service, or other aspects of human culture. Religions have sacred histories and narratives, which may be preserved in sacred scriptures and symbols and holy places, that aim mostly to give a meaning to life. Religions may contain symbolic stories which are sometimes said by followers to be true, that have the side purpose of explaining the origin of life, the universe and other things. Traditionally, faith in addition to reason has been considered a source of religious beliefs (Swindal: 2017).

Economy on the other hand, according to James, Liam, Andy and Manfred (2015) is an area of the production, distribution, or trade, and consumption of goods and services by different agents. Understood in its broadest sense, 'The economy is defined as a social domain that emphasizes the practices, discourses, and material expressions associated with the production, use, and management of resources'. Agents in economic activities can be individuals, businesses, organisations or governments. Economic transactions occur when two parties agree to the value or price of the transacted good or service, commonly expressed in a certain currency. However, monetary transactions only account for a small part of the economic domain.

In the opinion of Kartik (2017), a given economy is the result of a set of process that involves its culture, values, education, technological evolution, history, social organisation, political structure and legal systems, as well as its geography, natural resource endowment, and ecology, as main factors. These factors give context, content, and set the conditions and parameters in which an

economy functions. In other words, the economic domain is a social domain of human practices and transactions, it does not stand alone. Furthermore, a market-based economy is one where goods and services are produced and exchanged according to demand and supply between participants (economic agents) by barter or a medium of exchange with a credit or debit value accepted within the network, such as a unit of currency.

In summary, an economy is the large set of inter-related production and consumption activities that aid in determining how scarce resources are allocated. The production and consumption of goods and services are used to fulfill the needs of those living and operating within the economy, which is also referred to as an economic system (Kenton: 2019).

Impact of Religion on Economic Growth

It has been asserted that Religion has a noticeable impact in economic performance. This according to Andersen, Bentzen, Dalgaard and Sharp (2017) occurred throughout history; most notable is Weber's argument on the 'Protestant ethic'. This column uses an earlier example of the Cistercian Catholic Order to show that religious values did influence productivity and economic performance in England and across Europe. The effect of this historic influence has persisted until today.

The most famous work on how religion might impact on economic growth came from Max Weber who argued for the idea of a 'Protestant ethic'. In his work on protestant ethics and the spirit of Capitalism, Weber observes that the predominantly Protestant north of Europe was richer than the predominantly Catholic south, which could be traced back to Protestantism's promotion of the virtues of hard work and thrift. As a consequence, he believed that Protestants worked harder than their Catholic counterparts, and saved more – facilitating the rise of capitalism in Western Europe. The theory remains controversial till today, although it has recently been argued using data from Prussia, that it was Luther's idea that Christians should be able to read the Bible and the consequential impact on human capital accumulation, rather than a Protestant ethic as such, was the real reason why Protestants performed better than Catholics in that particular setting (Becker and Woessmann: 2009).

One other fundamental aspect that is common to all forms of religion is that they prescribe rules of behaviour or practices that constrain followers with varying degrees of strictness. First, religious practices impose an immediate trade-off as they require time and resources that are then unavailable for production. Second, they could also directly affect productivity, for instance by limiting social interactions with nonbelievers or by imposing dietary restrictions. Third, they may shape beliefs and values that determine economic decisions.

Religious liberty contributes to better business and economic outcomes. According to Grim, Clark and Edward (2014), it is believed that countries with lower levels of religious hostilities and government restrictions on religion ranked stronger in global competitiveness. Also Lipset and Lenz (2000) posit that religious freedom also contributes to peace and stability and helps lower corruption - two important ingredients for economic development. Research on Muslim majority countries has shown that high religious restrictions deter young entrepreneurs and allow business competitors to cite religious laws to attack their rivals (Ahmed and Mohamed: 2011).

Religion affects economic decision-making by establishing social standards and shaping individual personalities. Firms located in communities with higher religiosity tend to adhere to ethical norms that are conducive to a stable economy. In the words of Callen and Xiaohua (2015), companies or businesses situated in counties with higher religiosity had less instances of manager bad-news-holding and, correspondingly, significantly lower levels of future stock price crash risk. Purportedly, Adhikari and Anup (2015) posit that banks headquartered in areas with high religiosity also took less risk and experienced less value destruction in times of crisis. Researchers at Rice University reported that companies headquartered in highly religious areas had fewer instances of “misbehavior” than those in less religious communities, as measured by securities fraud lawsuits filed against the firm, aggressive earnings manipulation (Grullon, Kanatas and Weston: 2009).

According to Dyreng, Mayew, and Williams (2012), high religious adherence was also linked to a lower likelihood of financial restatement, less risk that financial statements were misrepresented, a lower likelihood of participating in tax sheltering, and more honesty in voluntary disclosures. Similarly, Jiang, Kose, Wei and Yiming (2016) affirmed that firms headquartered in religious areas had higher credit ratings and lower cost of debt. Also religious practice naturally and efficiently cultivates the human capital necessary for a thriving economy. Religiously involved students tend to spend more time on their homework, work harder in school and have higher educational aspirations. (Muller and Ellison: 2001). And is particularly powerful in helping disadvantaged youth in poor neighborhoods stay on-track in school and improve their educational status thereby helping to boost the economy (Regnerus: 2001).

Practically in his work, Hamilton (2011) opines that certain traditional, social and cultural values inspired by Confucianism has contributed to the business activities, enterprise management and economic development of contemporary Chinese societies. First, there are values of accepting and respecting authority inspired by the Confucian notions of ‘*xiao*’ (filial piety) and ‘*zhong*’ (loyalty) which had contributed to the management and functioning of Chinese enterprises and had formed a major driving force of the economic development of contemporary Chinese societies. In the same vein, the function of Confucianism in facilitating Chinese people’s acceptance of authority has contributed to legitimising authority and justifying the authority’s relations in modern Chinese business enterprises.

Secondly, some scholars have also pointed out that some values inspired by Confucianism have supported the authority of the centralised state bureaucracy and facilitated the acceptance of the leadership of bureaucratic elite. According to Ambrose King in Ivan (2019) the Chinese ruler had the traditional right and duty to intervene in the socio-economic activities of society; a duty ideologically justified by the Confucian notion of cosmically based universal kingship (Son of Heaven) based on the ‘Mandate of Heaven’. Krieger (1991) also points out the Confucian idea that government assumes full and comprehensive responsibility for the well-being of people while bureaucrats are not merely government functionaries but also leaders, intellectuals and teachers of the people who remain persuasive in East Asia.

Equally, the value of accepting the authority and leadership of bureaucratic state inspired by Confucianism has contributed to the political and social stability, the close business government relationships, as well as the acceptance of active government guidance of business activities and

economic development in ethnic Chinese societies, which were positive factors in their economic development in the late 20th Century.

Practical Examples of Religious Effect on Economy

In addition to the points mentioned above on the impacts of religion on the economic growth, it is worthy to posit here that religious organisations and activities accrue significant revenue in every Country's economy. In an analysis done by Brian and Melissa (2016), it was seen that faith-based organisations contributed \$378 billion annually to the U.S. economy based on revenue in education, healthcare, congregational activities, charities, media and food.

The Christian Church has in myriad ways contributed to the development of the economy. In the Christian setting, for instance, every Sunday witnesses crowd trooping in thousands into the Omega Power Ministry that is currently situated at Aluu community in Rivers State. There are people selling within and around the church premises with many customers patronising them. Thus this religious body within the community has contributed greatly in increasing the economy in that community in the sense that as much people come for religious purposes, they need those commodities to survive which in turn boost the economy. There is always a coconut service every last Friday of the month in the Church mentioned above which implies that everybody is expected to come to the vigil with his or her own coconut. On this said day, the sale of coconut is much needed which makes some people to embark on that, of which in return gives them the expected dividend which invariably helps in raising the economy. Similarly, the Adoration Ministry Enugu Nigeria being organised by Rev Fr. Ejike Mbaka records a large turnout of worshippers which in turn leads to much sales by businesses around and thereby improving the economy. In the Anglican Communion, the hosting of a synod in any town within a given Diocese is normally perceived as a blessing to the community. This is not only because of the spiritual blessing it ushers in but also due to increase in sales. For this reason, during the days of the Synod, large number of sellers flocked around and this invariably enhances the economy.

A restriction on any commodity by the Christian religious organisation, do hamper the economy in the sense that it affects the sales and also their economy. In regions where Christianity is dominant, commerce is largely tied to the intensity of the observance. The state of Utah's liquor regulations are a great example of the impact of conservative Christianity. In this region, the state government maintains tight control over the liquor industry and places strict limits on its sale and consumption. Businesses in regions where conservative Christianity prevails should ensure that their plans and projections are not based on retail sales of goods or services that are treated as sinful or evil.

When the Muslims embark on their pilgrimage, it is seen that it increases the economy of the host community and the state. This is so because with the influx of people, there are always buying and selling which help to improve the economy. Conversely, a restaurant or business situated within the Muslims enclave will yield no result during their fasting period. Also a prohibition on any commodity by the Muslims because of their religious persuasion and inclination will make that commodity not to thrive within their domain. International business in conservative Muslim regions will be impacted by a number of Islamic practices, including the religious dress code. In areas where women do not wear Western clothing and the Islamic dress code is passionately enforced, for example clothing retailers will need to adjust their inventory to

include things like burqua, niqabs, hijabs, and chadors. This shows the length at which religious practice and teaching can affect the State or nations economy.

Also according to Ivan (2019), when the economies of the East Asian areas influenced by Confucianism were rapidly developing in the late 20th Century, New Confucian scholars who were active in the Western academic circle at that time in response to Western scholars' questions on the cultural factors behind the economic development of East Asia as well as the relationships between Confucianism and economic development, argued that Confucianism was a driving force behind the rapid economic development of East Asia. They tried to draw a parallel with Max Weber's argument that Protestant ethics was a driving force behind the emergence of modern capitalism in the Western European areas influenced by Calvinism. In his conclusion, Ivan came to the summation that there are relationships between Confucianism and the economic development of contemporary Chinese societies which was seen on the rapid economic development of ethnic Chinese societies in the late 20th Century as facilitated by the disappearance or weakening of some social systems and values influenced by Confucianism, which had constrained the development of commerce and capitalism in pre-modern China.

Buddhist economic ethics according to Gokhale (1982) tends not to be just the reflection of religious attitudes toward the economy but also religious attitudes toward the state (polity). This latter relationship (Buddhism and the polity) usually was characterized by interdependence and reciprocity, that is, state support for the sangha in return for the sangha's spiritual protection and legitimisation of the state. The implication of this relationship for Buddhist economic ethics was that they usually (a) did not challenge or question the existing economic distribution of wealth but emphasised instead religious giving to the sangha (*daana*) as the ideal social action; and (b) relied upon secular authorities to help define the specifics of lay Buddhist economic ethics, along with guidelines given in various sutra. Buddhist economic ethics for the laity were not inherently antagonistic to the development of capitalism, but in fact supported a primitive capitalism among the merchant classes in early Buddhist India, and medieval China and Japan. This could be seen in both merchant-type lay ethics, which encouraged the accumulation of wealth along with certain restraints on consumption of this wealth, and direct economic activities by Buddhist monasteries themselves, which led to innovations in business practices and implicit support for commercial tendencies in society as a whole.

Thus, in the word of Gernet (1995), Buddhism's role in the economic development of these three countries was to encourage lay accumulation of wealth and productive labour. Official doctrine seldom varied in ultimately viewing such lay wealth and labour as less important than activities directly related to monk enlightenment or lay merit making through *daana*. As a result, while Buddhist lay ethics may have helped provide the necessary type of lay values for the development of modernization and modern capitalism (in Japan for example), these ethics were not *sufficient* factors in themselves to propel such development. Moreover, while Buddhist believers and institutions were not the initiators of the political, social and economic changes which led to economic modernisation in Japan in particular, this does not eliminate a certain Buddhist 'flavour' to the strong work ethic and almost religious view of work which has supported the development of modernisation and modern capitalism in Japan.

Coming home to the African culture, it is seen that the culture is an embodiment of tourism itself through its preservation, promotion and presentation to boost the economy. The New Yam (*Iri*

Ji) Festivals such as celebrated in Igbo Ukwu, Nri and other parts of Igbo land, Nigeria contributes to economic growth. This festival honours the earth goddess and the ancestral spirits of the land. Sons and daughters return home for this occasion thereby contributing to economic growth through purchases. Other cultural carnivals such as Calabar Carnival festival in Nigeria, also tagged Africa's Biggest Street Party are evidence that African traditional culture has enhanced cultural tourism and boost the economy in Nigeria. African Traditional Religion (ATR) through its great potentials unlocks the growth and development aspirations of the nation.

Conclusion

Historically, religion which is a systematic set of beliefs that influences human behaviour, has been a dominant force in the society. For most individuals, religion is about how to live and people adopt its system's beliefs as a way of life. Religion's influence reaches every corner of the globe and it significantly influences the buying behaviours of customers. Some religious restrictions can directly affect economic activity, creating legal barriers for import and export industries such as the halal food market. Proscriptive laws can also stoke region-wide religious hostilities, again disrupting markets.

Religion as we can see from the discussion is a veritable tool for national development which is so because it has much impact on the economy of every state on which it is practice, be it any religion. It does not only boast the economy but also helps in creating a better avenue for legitimate economic activities and friendship in business. It creates and instills an ethical norm and consciousness in people by restricting them on the acceptable business to transact in order to still have a better relationship with the ultimate reality and receive a better reward at the end of life. Economy on the other hand does affect religion and the religionist in many ways. According to Riegg (2017) "Salat" is the Arabic word for the prayer time that Muslims are asked to perform five times a day. During the usual workday, Salat occurs about four times and in most countries is voluntary. In the oil-rich monarchy, all businesses are required to shut down during Salat to give their employees enough time to go to a local mosque and pray. During the 1980s, if Saudi's religious police caught a young Muslim outside during Salat, they will literally drag him to a mosque.

In the white-collar economy, each Salat normally takes 15 minutes, because fancy office buildings usually have designated prayer rooms where employees can go. However, in most of the service industry (restaurants, gas stations, shops, etc.), businesses could be closed between 30 minutes and one hour at a time, to give their workers enough time to shut down, walk to the mosque, walk back, and open up again. Or, as was more often the case, to give their employees enough time to go hang out somewhere, have a few cigarettes, and complain about their bosses. Businesses that were frequently targeted by the religious police, or that had employees who were particularly religious might close early or wait until the last religious police patrol had rolled by to open back up. So it is seen that religion does affect the economy and the economy also affects religion.

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